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Review Article

A Review on Herbal Face Pack for Glowing Skin

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this Herbal Face Pack is work to create and test an herbal face pack for glowing skin using the all natural ingredients. The Natural Face Pack contains some of uses for our skin healthy. The aim of this work is to formulate and evaluate an herbal face pack for glowing skin by using natural herbal ingredients. The natural herbal ingredients such as multani mitti, turmeric, sandalwood, saffron, milk powder, rice flour, orange peel, neem were purchased from local market in the form of dried powder. The main objective of this article is to formulate and evaluate an natural herbal face pack for glowing skin by using natural ingredients in varying concentrations, ingredients such as. Ayurvedic formulations are safer than synthetic formulation because its side effect is very low. The main purpose of Herbal face packs are to remove the dark circle, Pimples through the increase blood circulation and maintained it and the cover the skin and remove dirt particles from the skin pores.

INTRODUCTION

The main use of herbal cosmetic is that it is pure and does not have any side effects on the human body. In this article we have formulated herbal face pack to whiten, lighten and brighten the skin naturally for men and women. This face pack has natural skin lightening property and can be easily prepared at home. Natural facial packs are easy to use. Present article deals with the formulation and evaluation of herbal face pack for glowing skin by using natural materials i.e., multani mitti, turmeric, sandal wood, saffron, milk powder, rice flour,

orange peel, banana peel and rose water. Now a days, The Herbs are widely used as remedial agents because herbs are easily available at less expensive. The herbs are used from the ancient time for cleaning, beautifying and the treatment of various skin disease. The skin of the face is the major part of the body but some common skin diseases are Acne, black head, pimples, dark circle are seen in youngsters and these dark circle reduce the fairness of the face. In previous times, the women were very conscious about their beauty and treat the facial skin problems through the

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medicated herbs like as neem, aloe vera, tulsi, orange peel, rose and some for blood purification herbs like Chandana, Turmeric. The herbal cosmetic are main advantages, it is pure and does not have any side effects on the human body.

classified into the following categories-

1. Plastic masks: Wax based, latex based, or vinyl based
 2. Hydrocolloid masks: Gel masks
 3. Argillaceous masks: Clay based or earth based
- Benefits Of Face Pack:

- 1.The harmful effects of pollution and harsh climates can be reduced by the use of face pack.
2. It helps to reduce, acne, pimple, scars and marks depending on its herbal ingredients.
3. Its help to remove the dead cells from skin.
4. These are providing a soothing and relaxing effect on skin.
- 5.They are helps to Glowing skin.
- 6.The Face pack is provide Nourishment to the skin.

Precautions:

1. The face pack is used according to your skin type.
2. Concerned to the skin expert before use of any natural therapy on face.
3. Maximum 20-25 min stay on face and after that wash the face and completely remove the medicaments.
4. It should be completely dried.
5. Avoid applying face pack near "eye zone" because the skin around eye is very soft. The process of removing face pack may damage skin around the eyes so apply careful.

Materials and Methods:

Present article deals with the formulation and evaluation of herbal face pack for glowing skin by using natural ingredient i.e., multani mitti, turmeric, sandalwood, saffron, milk powder, rice flour, orange peel and Neem. They were purchased from local market in the form of dried powder.

Ingredients of formulations:

1.Multani Mitti

Scientific name: Fullers Earth

Synonym: Multani Mitti

Use: Fight acne and pimples

Multani mitti helps skin by different ways like diminishing pore sizes, removing blackheads and soothing sunburns, cleansing skin, improving blood circulation, complexion, reducing acne and blemishes and gives a glowing effect to a skin as they contain healthy nutrients. Multani mitti is rich magnesium chloride.

2. Turmeric (Curuma)

Family: Zin giberaceae

Use: Antiseptic

Turmeric has been used in this preparation due to its blood purifying property and helps in wound healing, because of its antiseptic action. It cures the skin diseases occurring due to blood impurities. It is a very good anti-inflammatory and anti-allergic agent. The phyto constituents, It helps to lighten the skin tone. Turmeric delays the signs of aging like wrinkles, improves skin elasticity.

3.Sandal Wood

Family: Santalaceae

Synonym: Sandal

Use: Anti-aging, acne treatment

4.Saffron

Mainly consists of dried stigmas and upper parts of styles of plant known as *Crocus sativus*, belonging to the family Iridaceae. It is rich in carotenoid glycosides, mainly containing terpenoids. It lightens the skin tone and provides fair and glowing skin.

5. Milk Powder:

Milk powder is very beneficial for skin, as it provides nourishment for dry, rough skin for the longer duration. Milk cream either in the form of powdered raw milk or milk as such provides a brilliant shine to skin. This is beneficial in hydrating the face deeply and makes skin youthful, lustrous and flawless. It bleaches the skin to remove dark spots, pigmentation, acne etc. This pack also removes blackheads, whiteheads, and other skin imperfections naturally. This facial pack helps in fading sun tan.

6.Rice Flour:

Rice flour can be applied to cure some forms of skin ailments. In Indian subcontinent, rice water is duly prescribed by Ayurvedic practitioners as in undigested form. It aids the growth of useful bacteria for normal bowel movements an effective ointment to cool off inflamed skin surfaces.

7.Neem:

Family: Meliaceae

Scientific name: *Melia Indica*

Use: Antibacterial Properties

8. Rose Powder:

Synonyms: Rosettes

Source: Flowers of the genus *Rosa* in the family Rosaceae.

Uses: Natural moisturizer, reduce redness.

Procedure for application of face pack

The pack should be applied daily on wet face, forming a paste of it in water with optimum thickness. It should be applied evenly on the face with the help of a brush. It should be left for 15 minutes for complete drying. Then it should be removed with the help of a wet sponge.

Evaluation of face pack

1. Morphological Evaluation

It refers to the evaluation of the herbal face pack by its color, odor, appearance, texture etc. The external characters of the formulation is examined based on the method described by Siddiqui et al.

2. Physicochemical evaluation

Physicochemical parameters were determined, including the determination of extractive value, ash value, pH and moisture content etc.

3. Physical evaluation

The particle size was tested by microscopy method. The flow property of the dried powder of combined form. was evaluated by performing Angle of Repose by funnel method, bulk density and tapped density by Tapping Method.

4. Phytochemical evaluation.

The aqueous extract of the herbal face pack was evaluated for the presence of different phytoconstituents as per the standard procedures.

5. Irritancy test.

Mark an area (1sq.cm) on the left-hand dorsal surface. Definite quantities of prepared face packs were applied to the specified area and time was noted. Irritancy, erythematic, edema, was checked if any for regular intervals up to 24 hrs and reported. Stability, Studies- Stability testing of prepared formulation was conducted by storing at different temperature conditions for the period of one month. The packed glass vials of formulation stored at different temperature conditions like, room temperature and 40°C and were evaluated for physical parameters like color, odour, pH, consistency and feel.

CONCLUSION

Natural remedies are more acceptable in the belief that they are safer with side effects than the synthetic ones. Herbal formulations have growing demand in the world market. Herbal face packs are used to increase blood circulation, rejuvenate the muscles and help to maintain the elasticity of the skin and remove dirt from skin. It is a our good attempt to formulate the herbal face pack containing natural herbal ingredients such as multani mitti, turmeric, sandal wood, saffron, milk powder, rice flour, orange peel and rose powder. After evaluation, we found good properties for the face packs, free from skin irritation and maintained its consistency even after stability storage conditions. It has been revealed that herbal face pack having enough potential to give efficient glowing effect on skin. The overall study is useful to substantiate product claims due its useful benefits on the human beings

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